

GREEN ADMINISTRATIVE SKILL MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN MANUFACTURING FIRM SOUTH NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the effect of Green Administrative Skill Management on Employee Performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria. The specific objectives are to; examine the effect of communication skills on employee performance and evaluate the effect of time management skills on employee performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria. A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. A structured questionnaire design with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect primary data for the study. Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The result revealed that communication skill significantly impacts employee performance with a P-value of ($p=0.000$) while time management skills have a significant impact on employee performance with a P-value of ($p = 0.003$) in Manufacturing firms in South Nigeria. We concluded that Green Administrative Skill Management has a significant effect on Employee Performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria. We recommended that Manufacturing firms should prioritize the development of communication skills training programs aimed at enhancing employees' ability to effectively convey and receive information related to environmental sustainability initiatives.

Keywords: Administration, Employee, Green, Management, Performance, Skill

1.1 Introduction

The dynamic nature of modern business has made the relationship between employee performance and organizational procedures a subject of ongoing examination and development. When it comes to industrial companies, where productivity and environmentally friendly methods are critical, including (Emenike, Ibobo, and Akerejola, 2022). Green Administrative Skill Management (GASM) becomes a critical component of worker productivity. The General Anthropocentric Systems Model (GASM) is a comprehensive strategy for managing human resources in manufacturing organizations (Emenike, Ibobo, and Akerejola, 2022). It includes adopting environmentally conscious policies, developing green leadership traits, and encouraging sustainable behaviors at all organizational levels. In this setting, the importance of Green Administrative Skill Management (GASM) has drawn more attention as a tactical means of encouraging environmental responsibility and improving worker performance and operational efficiency (Maduko and Puche, 2020).

The significance of GASM in manufacturing firms stems from its ability to align organizational objectives with ecological imperatives while simultaneously enhancing employee engagement, productivity, and overall performance. By nurturing a culture of environmental responsibility and equipping employees with the requisite skills and knowledge to navigate the complexities of sustainability (Emenike, Ibobo, and Akerejola, 2022). GASM empowers manufacturing firms to achieve a competitive edge in an increasingly eco-conscious market landscape. Gaining insight into how GASM affects employee performance in Southeast Nigeria manufacturing firms—where environmental stewardship and economic development converge—will have a significant impact on the competitiveness and sustainability of the business (Bode, 2020). Manufacturing firms in South Nigeria operate within a complex ecosystem characterized by rapid industrialization, resource constraints, and evolving regulatory frameworks. Against this backdrop, the integration of GASM principles into administrative practices represents a proactive response to the imperatives of sustainable development and corporate social responsibility. GASM encompasses a range of administrative skills and strategies aimed at minimizing environmental impacts, optimizing resource utilization, and cultivating a culture of sustainability within the organization (Maduko and Puche, 2020).

The nexus between GASM and employee performance embodies a symbiotic relationship wherein environmentally conscious administrative practices not only contribute to ecological preservation but also engender a conducive work environment conducive to employee well-being, engagement, and productivity (Bode, 2020). By embracing GASM, manufacturing firms in South Nigeria have the opportunity to leverage their administrative capacities as catalysts for positive organizational change, thereby fostering a virtuous cycle of environmental stewardship and enhanced employee performance. Against this backdrop, this study seeks to investigate the effect of Green Administrative Skill Management on Employee Performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The term "green administrative skill management" (GASM) refers to the collection of abilities, tactics, and procedures managers and organizational leaders use to incorporate environmental sustainability concepts into decision-making and administrative procedures. It entails the methodical implementation of ecologically friendly techniques to improve organizational effectiveness, lessen environmental effects, and advance sustainable development. Within the Southeast Nigerian industrial sector, knowledge is deficient regarding the effects of Green Administrative Skill Management (GASM) on worker productivity. Even while businesses all over the world are placing more and more attention on sustainable practices, there is still a dearth of thorough studies that notably examine how GASM affects worker performance in Nigeria's industrial sector, especially in the southeast. Manufacturing companies find it more difficult to optimize and implement green administrative procedures to improve employee engagement, productivity, and overall performance due to a lack of communication skills among leaders and a lack of time management skills with this knowledge gap. Investigating the connection between GASM and worker performance in the particular socioeconomic and environmental setting of Southeast Nigeria's industrial sector is therefore crucial. By offering practical insights that can guide strategic decision-

making and enhance organizational performance in the interest of sustainability and worker wellbeing, our research seeks to close this knowledge gap.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of Green Administrative Skill Management on Employee Performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

- i. Examine the effect of communication skills on employee performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of time management skills on employee performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.

1.4 Hypotheses of the Study

- i. Communication skills do not have a significant effect on employee performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.
- ii. Time management skills have no significant effect on employee performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Administrative Skills

The other related concept that has been advocated for improved performance is the acquisition of administrative skills by school heads. In the opinion of Okeke (2006), wherever people are organized in such a way as to attain certain specific goal(s) the elements of administration will come into play. This could be the school, the church, business organizations, and even the family. Administration therefore is geared towards goal attainment and goal accomplishment.

Ijeoma (2004) viewed administration as a process of directing the utilization of material and human resources to accomplish the predetermined goals of an organization. The activities involved in the pursuit of goals to meet a variety of human needs are carried out in organizations. These organizations are distinguished by their specific goals. One can therefore speak of general and specific functions of administration. The general functions are applicable across all organizations. The specific functions derive from the goals and objectives of a particular type of organization. The two reflect the domains of theory and practice respectively. Administration is generally defined as the process of working with and through others to efficiently accomplish organizational goals. It is the art and science of getting things efficiently done (Omemu, 2015).

Skill or competence is perceived to mean the ability to do something well. Administrative skill therefore is viewed as the special competence and ability of school administrators as well as all others to perform their duties effectively and efficiently toward goal achievement in organizations. The reason why administrators such as the head teachers need to possess sufficient skills in administration is to enable them to achieve organizational goals as planned (Omemu, 2015). Katz (1955) and cited by Peretomode (2003) identified three basic skills upon which, in his opinion, effective performance and consequently, successful administration rest. These skills are quite

interdependent though they are often treated separately for purely analytical purposes. The basic skills are identified as technical, human, and conceptual skills (Omemu, 2015).

Green Skills

Green skill is referred to as skills for sustainable development. Green skills are regarded as skills for sustainability that are related to the technical skills, knowledge, values, and attitudes needed in the workforce to develop and support sustainable social, economic, and environmental outcomes in business, industry, and the community. Likewise, CEDEFOP defines green skills as the knowledge, abilities, values, and attitudes needed to live in, develop, and support a society that reduces the impact of human activity on the environment. Taken together, green skills are generally composed of three dimensions, namely, knowledge (cognitive dimension), skills/abilities (psychomotor dimension), and attitudes/values (affective dimension) needed by workers to promote sustainable development in society, economy, and environment. From the cognitive dimension, knowledge concerning environmental protection can be regarded as an element of green skills. From a psychomotor perspective, green skill refers to the ability to, for instance, minimize energy consumption, or reduce greenhouse gases. Green skills also refer to the affective aspect, for example, the motivation of an individual to conserve natural resources (Heong, Sern, Kiong, and Mohamad, 2016).

Green Administrative Skills

Green administrative skill is defined as the competencies and abilities required by administrative personnel to effectively manage and implement environmental sustainability initiatives within organizations. Green administrative skill management refers to the systematic approach of identifying, developing, and utilizing administrative competencies that support environmental sustainability goals within organizations (Heong, Sern, Kiong, and Mohamad, 2016). Green administrative skill management is essential for organizations committed to environmental sustainability. By prioritizing the development and utilization of green administrative competencies, organizations can enhance their environmental performance, meet stakeholder expectations, and achieve long-term success. Through strategic planning, targeted training, adequate communication, and continuous improvement efforts, organizations can effectively embed sustainability principles into their administrative practices, contributing to a greener and more sustainable future (Heong, Sern, Kiong, and Mohamad, 2016).

Communication skills

Kambe (2011) defined communication skills as the ability to convey the message effectively to subordinates. Communication skills for managers are an important factor for effective management in an organization. The manager needs to communicate knowledge, instructions, purpose, goal, mission, and vision of the organization to the employees. The communication includes verbal and nonverbal skills. The manager must be able to communicate the plans and policies to the employees, similarly, he must listen and solve the problems of the employees, and he must encourage a free flow of communication in the organization.

Nebo, Nwankwo, and Okonkwo (2015) argued that communication is a means of bringing about change, it is the mainstream of any organization's growth. Communication is a process of transmitting information from one

person to another. According to Stephen (2011), communication is a critical factor in directing and mobilizing the workforce toward the accomplishment of organizational goals or objectives. Communication can be seen as a reduction of uncertainty thus communication is an exchange of meaning. Asamu (2014) pointed out that the beginning of the universe was the beginning of communication, there was no beginning that was devoid of communication. Thus communication facilitates the transformation of human society, communication is a many-sided phenomenon that means different things to different people. It is a process or a means of accessing the minds of thoughts of another.

Communication is a process by which any person or group shares and impacts information with/ to another person (or group) so that both people (and group) clearly understand one another. Communication is important at all levels of the organization. The ability to communicate effectively, both verbally and non-verbally is crucial for effective leadership. Poor communication skills can lead to misunderstandings and conflicts. This skill helps individuals know when, how, and what to communicate. Through good communication skills, managers can create an environment within his or her team that encourages creativity and innovation (Maduko and Puche, 2020).

Communication skills should be stressed that communication is best achieved through simple planning and control, especially at meetings where conversations need particular care. To ensure an efficient and effective conversation, certain considerations require leaders in organizations to constantly pay attention in the first place, leaders must make sure that the intended message sent is received and understood. Secondly, they must exert some control over the flow of the communication. However, learning to listen patiently as well as to speak lucidly are effective communication skills for managers in democratic settings (Maduko and Puche, 2020). Those who dismiss these as a mere platitude are already demonstrating an indisposition to listening, the phrase must be trite, but the message is hugely significant for effectiveness as a manager. The skill of listening must be explicitly developed to enable leaders to hear the suggestion/ information which should launch them to fame and fortune. A manager in a corporate organization must avoid being ambitious. In other words, the manager must be pragmatic rather than philosophical. Thus, words mean not what the dictionary says but rather what the speaker intended (Bode, 2020).

Time Management Skills

Time management is all about control and balance. It is the process of planning your tasks and objectives within a certain timeframe and regulating your performance in a way that fosters an optimal use of time resources (Emenike, Ibobo, and Akerejola, 2022). Time is an essential resource, it's irrecoverable, limited, and dynamic. It is irrevocable because every minute spent is gone forever, limited because only 24 hours exist in a day, and dynamic because it's never static. According to North (2004), time management is the organization of tasks or events by first estimating how much time a task will take to be completed, when it must be completed, and then adjusting events that would interfere with its completion is reached in the appropriate amount of time.

Time management is not about getting more things done in a day. It is about getting the things that matter most done. Time management is the ability to decide what is important in your life both at work, at home, and even in

your personal life. Time is that quality of nature that keeps all events from happening at once. To manage your time, you need to go through a personal time survey and estimate the way your time is being spent. Time management is a set of principles, practices, skills, tools, and systems that help you use your time to accomplish what you want. Time management is a skill that many of us seem to learn through necessity (Emenike, Ibobo, and Akerejola, 2022).

Employee performance

Performance is the result obtained by an organization both profit-oriented and non-profit-oriented organizations produced over a certain period (Fahmi, 2016). Meanwhile, according to Torang (2013), performance (performance) is the quantity and or quality of the work of individuals or groups in the organization in carrying out basic tasks and functions based on standard operational procedures, criteria, and measurements that have been set or applicable in the organization. According to Moehariono, (2012), performance or performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of a program of activities or policies in realizing the goals, objectives, vision, and mission of the organization set in strategic planning. Rivai & Sagala (2011) define performance as real behavior displayed by everyone as work performance produced by employees in their respective roles in the company. Performance is basically what is done or what is not done by employees (Mathis & Jackson, 2006). Employee performance indicators in this study use criteria in performance measurement which was also stated by Wirawan (2013) consisting of 1) quantity of work, 2) quality, 3) timeliness of implementation or completion of work, 4) effectiveness of using resources organization, 5) methods of carrying out work.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Social Exchange Theory (SET)

Social exchange theory (SET) is among the most influential paradigms for understanding workplace behavior. Although different views of social exchange have emerged, theorists agree that social exchange involves a series of interactions that generate obligations (Emerson, 1976). Within SET, these interactions are usually seen as interdependent and contingent on the actions of another person (Blau, 1964). SET also emphasizes that these interdependent transactions have the potential to generate high-quality relationships (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Blau (1964) was among the first to differentiate social and economic exchange. According to Blau, social exchange refers to relationships that entail unspecified future obligations. Like economic exchange, social exchange generates an expectation of some future return for contributions; however, unlike economic exchange, the exact nature of that return is unspecified. Furthermore, social exchange does not occur on a quid pro quo or calculated basis, implying social exchange creates enduring social patterns. Economic exchange is based on transactions, but social exchange relationships are based on individuals' trusting that the other parties to the exchange will fairly discharge their obligations in the long run. This trust is necessary for maintaining social exchange, especially in the short run, where some temporary or perceived asymmetries may exist between an individual's inducements – that is, the benefits received from participation in the social exchange relationship – and contributions, the individual's input into the relationship. Furthermore, the expectation of long-term fairness

in social exchange contrasts with the expectation of short-term fairness that typically characterizes economic exchange (Konovsky & Pugh, 1994).

One of the basic tenets of SET is that relationships evolve into trusting, loyal, and mutual commitments. To do so, parties must abide by certain “rules” of exchange. Rules of exchange, describe a “normative definition of the situation that forms among or is adopted by the participants in an exchange relation” (Emerson, 1976). In this way, rules and norms of exchange are “the guidelines” of exchange processes (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Investment and trust are intertwined in exchange relationships. Specifically, in social exchanges, both parties invest in the other party with some inherent risk that the investment will not be repaid, requiring trust (Blau, 1964). Another basic tenet of SET is that social exchange requires a long-term orientation since the exchange is ongoing and based on feelings of obligation. Furthermore, another basic tenet of SET is the emphasis on the socio-emotional (i.e., feelings of obligation and trust) aspect of the exchange (Shore et al., 2006).

SET was originally developed to account for the development and maintenance of interpersonal relationships. It has since been applied to workplace relationships or the employment relationship. Of special interest to social exchange theorists are differences in the parties involved in the relationship. The general presumption is that workers can form distinguishable social exchange relationships, with immediate supervisors, co-workers, and employing organizations. These distinct relationships have implications for behavior. Specifically, because individuals return the benefits they receive, they are likely to match goodwill and helpfulness toward the party with whom they have a social exchange relationship (Cropanzano & Mitchell 2005).

As a set of practices that entail investment in employees and opportunities to perform, HPWS signals an organization’s interest in maintaining a long-term relationship with its employees and also emphasizes the socio-emotional (e.g., being taken care of by the organization) aspects of the exchange. This creates feelings of obligation on the part of the employee, and because individuals return the benefits they receive, employees are likely to reciprocate the organization’s favorable treatment with behaviors that promote its goal-attainment efforts. As depicted in Figure 1, I tested the formulations of SET in this study by examining perceived organizational support (POS) as a mechanism through which experienced HPWS influence service OCB.

2.3 Empirical Review

Antara, Sitiari, and Sarmawa (2021) studied the effect of time management and communication on employee performance with mediation of work motivation. This study aimed to examine employee performance through time management, communication, and work motivation was conducted at the Kepeng Money Craft Industry in Kamasan Village, Klungkung District, which involved all 40 company employees as research respondents. This research was conducted in a census. The distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents is the method used in collecting the data, then the data is processed using the Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Square (PLS) method, through the SmartPLS 3.0 program, at a significance level of 0.05 (5%). The results of this study found that time management, communication, and work motivation each had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Time management has a significant positive effect on work motivation. Time management has a significant positive effect on employee performance. Communication has a significant positive

effect on work motivation. Communication has a significant positive effect on employee performance. Work motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance. Work motivation mediates some of the effects of time management on employee performance. Work motivation mediates some of the effects of communication on the performance of employees of the kepeng handicraft industry in Kamasan Village, Klungkung Regency.

Vercic (2021) studied the impact of employee engagement, organizational support, and employer branding on internal communication satisfaction. The study intended to provide further insight into the relationship between the various concepts connected to internal communication practices. To do this, 1805 employees from 12 large corporations in Croatia participated in a national study exploring the relationship between employee engagement, employer brand, perceived organizational support, and internal communication satisfaction. The results showed a significant and positive relationship between all measured variables. Regression analysis suggests that three independent variables (employee engagement, employer brand measured through employer attractiveness, and perceived organizational support) predicted and explained 78.9 percent of the variation in internal communication satisfaction.

Lee, Kang, Kim, and Yang (2022) investigated how employee–organization relationship (EOR) outcomes – types and qualities – are interrelated and how employees' perceptions of types (exchange and communal EORs) and qualities (trust, satisfaction, commitment, and control mutuality) play a role in their evaluations of symmetrical internal communication (SIC) and employee job engagement (EJE). This study conducted an online survey of full-time employees ($N = 804$) from major US industries. This study performed a confirmatory factor analysis to check the validity and reliability of the measurement model using latent variables and then conducted structural equation modeling. The findings demonstrate that employees' perceptions of both exchange and communal EORs are associated with each of the four EOR qualities. The results also show that only communal EORs have a significant relationship with perceived SIC and that employees' perceptions about one of the EOR quality indicators, satisfaction with an organization, had a significant association with their perceived EJE.

Emenike, Ibobo, and Akerejola (2022) examined the impact of time management on Employee performance in some selected organizations in Edo State. The study precisely evaluated how adherence to time by employees impacts performance in selected organizations in Edo State. Two research hypotheses were stated to guide the study, Pearson Product Correlation (PPC) technique was utilized to determine the parameter estimate in the two constructs. The PPC for the adherence to time on employee performance is significant with a correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.413 and indicates its statistical significance to employee performance. Similarly, the PPC for controlling of distractions to reduce time wastage on employee performance is significant. The correlation coefficient(r) which is the impact of controlling the distraction to reduce time wastage on employee performance is 0.511. The population of the study was 535 with a sample of 229 obtained from utilizing the Taro Yamane formula. Findings indicated that each of the identified variables are positive and significantly correlated to the dependent variable showing their importance to corporate organization in the selected study area in Edo State.

3. Methodology

The research design for this study was essentially descriptive to enable the researcher to investigate the statement of the problem under study. Descriptive research is research that specifies the nature of a given phenomenon. It applies a systematic explanation of situations. This type of research is expected to help in decision-making. They are prerequisites for inferences and generalizations. The research involves the selection of specific numbers of manufacturing firms within the southeastern region from which the desired number of respondents were chosen in order to investigate the effect of Green Administration Skill Management on Employee Performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria. The respondents received the appropriate and sufficient instructions they needed to complete the survey. Sections include:

Section A: Demographic characteristics

Demographic characteristics on which data were collected include gender, age, marital status, and highest level of education.

Section B

This section contains questions on the constructs – Communication skills, Time management skills, and employee performance. The three constructs were measured using a 4 - 4-point Likert scale where “1” = Strongly Agree (SA), “2” = Agree (A), “3” = Disagree (D), and “4” = Strongly Disagree (SD). The Cronbach Alpha reliability test was used to determine the questionnaire's internal consistency and reliability. Since the scale's alpha values were higher than 0.7, all the constructs showed high reliability. Cronbach alpha should be greater than 0.7, according to Nunnally [1]. Table 2 provides a summary of the reliability analysis.

Table 2: Summary of Cronbach's Alpha levels for the construct

Variable name	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items	Decision
Communication skill	0.708	5	Fit for use
Time management skills	0.823	6	Fit for use
Employee performance	0.767	5	Fit for use

Questionnaire Administration

With the help of some trained research assistants, copies of the questionnaire were self-administered throughout the southeastern state. The study's participants were assured of their confidentiality and were made aware of this fact by each research assistant, a finite population of 853 was obtained from the firm's human resource department, after which a total sample of 272 was obtained for the study using the Taro Yamane formula. 272 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 237 questionnaires were returned which accounted for an 87% return rate of the questionnaire.

4. Data Analysis techniques

Data collected were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). While descriptive statistics was used to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, Simple linear regression analyses were used for further analysis. All the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Socio-Demographic Information of Respondents

This section presents information about the sex, age of respondents, marital status, and highest educational qualification of respondents (Table 3). The information provided here was analyzed using frequency count and percentage.

Table 3: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

All	Demography characteristics	Frequency	Percent (%)
Sex	Male	197	83%
	Female	40	17%
Age of respondents	Under 20	17	07%
	20 - 29	67	28%
	30 – 39	72	30%
	40 – 49	53	22%
	50 – 59	18	08%
	60 and above	10	04%
Marital status	Single	137	58%
	Married	89	36%
	Separated/Divorced	09	04%
	Widowed	02	01%
Highest Educational Qualification	Primary Education	17	07%
	Senior Secondary School	28	12%
	NCE	30	13%
	HND	49	21%
	Bachelor’s degree	71	30%
	Post Graduate Qualification	21	09%
	Others	21	09%

Table 3 is the demographic profile of the respondents which reveals a predominantly male composition, with males comprising 197 out of a total of 237 participants, accounting for 83% of the sample. In terms of marital status, the majority of participants are single, constituting 58% of the sample, while 36% are married. The age distribution shows that the largest portion of participants falls within the 30-39 age group, with 72 individuals

(30%), followed closely by the 20-29 age group, comprising 67 individuals (28%). The representation decreases with age, with only 4% of participants being 60 years and above. Regarding academic qualifications, the sample demonstrates a varied educational background, with the highest proportion holding a Bachelor's degree (71 individuals, 30%), followed by HND (Higher National Diploma) at 49 individuals (21%) and NCE (Nigerian Certificate in Education) at 30 individuals (13%). Other qualifications include Senior Secondary School (28 individuals, 12%), Postgraduate degrees (21 individuals, 9%), and 21 individuals (9%) with qualifications classified as "Others".

In summary, the demographic profile showcases a predominantly male, relatively young, and well-educated sample. The majority of participants are single, with a significant portion having attained at least a Bachelor's degree. The age distribution skews towards younger age groups, with the highest representation in the 20-39 range, indicating a younger demographic profile. This data provides valuable insights for understanding the characteristics and composition of the sample population, which can be essential for various research or decision-making purposes.

Results

The test for the various study objectives is presented in this section. These individual objectives were examined using linear regression analysis. The analyses of linear regression were conducted using the Enter method. The findings are listed below:

Objective One:

Communication skills do not have a significant effect on employee performance in Manufacturing firms in Southeast Nigeria.

The ANOVA table (Table 4) shows that at 0.05 level of significance, the model is significant for predicting the impact of communication skills on employee performance ($F = 29.618$; $p = 0.002$) among the several selected firms in southeast Nigeria. There exists a low correlation between the observed and predicted values of the variable, economy of the community ($R = 247$), whereas only 21.99% (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.2199$) of the variance for respondents' employee performance was accounted for by communication skill (Table 5).

Table 4: Anova Table showing the goodness of fit table

Model		Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	33.297	1	33.297	29.618	0.002
	Residual	265.321	236	1.1242		
	Total	298.618	237			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication skill

Table 5: Predictive Power of communication skill on employee performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std Error of Estimate
1	0.247	0.311	0.2199		1.61360

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication skill

Notwithstanding, Table 6 indicates that communication skill significantly impacts employee performance ($p=0.000$). For every unit increase in communication skills, the employee performance increases by 0.301.

Table 6: Impact of communication Skills on employee performance

Mode		Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	T	Sig
		B	St. Error	Beta		
1	Constant	2.922	0.038		97.40	0.000
	Communication skill	0.301	0.0102	0.292	29.51	0.000

Dependent Variable: Employee performance

Objective Two:

Time management skills have no significant effect on employee performance in Manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.

Table 7 shows that the model is significant for predicting the health of the people in the benefitting communities ($F = 21.371$; $p = 0.003$). However, Table 8 shows that the correlation between the observed and predicted values of the variable, the health of the benefitting community is low ($R=0.300$). Moreover, only 50.1% ($\text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.501$) of the variance for employee performance was accounted for by time management skills.

Table 7: Anova Table showing the goodness of fit table

Model		Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	17.003	1	17.003	21.371	0.003
	Residual	187.763	236	0.7956		
	Total	204.766	237			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Time management skill

Table 8: Predictive Power of the time management skill on the economy performance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std Error of Estimate
1	0.300	0.589	0.501		2.34958

a. Predictors: (Constant), Time management skill

Table 9 however indicates that the employee performance in the firms is significantly influenced by time management skills ($p=0.003$). As the employee performance increases by 0.284 for every unit increases in time management skills. In this case, we agree that time management skill has an impact on employee performance across the study area.

Table 9: Impact of time management skill on the employee performance

Mode		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig
		coefficient	St. Error	coefficient		
1		B		Beta		
1	Constant	14.42	2.3380		6.190	0.000
	Time management skill	0.284	0.102	0.292	2.778	0.007

Dependent Variable: Employee performance

Summary For Abstract Use

H1: Communication skills do not have a significant effect on employee performance in manufacturing firms in Southeast Nigeria.

$\beta_0 = 2.922$

$\beta_1 = 0.301$; P-value = 0.000 < 0.05

R Square = 0.311 (31.1%)

F (1, 236) = 29.618, $p < 0.05$ (This is showing that the model 1 is significant)

H2: Time management skills have no significant effect on employee performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.

$\beta_0 = 14.42$

$\beta_2 = 0.284$; P-value = 0.007

R Square = 0.589 (58.9%)

F (1, 236) = 21.372, $p < 0.05$ (This is showing that model 2 is significant)

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the implementation of Green Administrative Skill Management (GASM) in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria holds significant potential to positively influence employee performance. This conclusion is reinforced by the acknowledgment that communication skills and time management skills play pivotal roles in shaping employee performance within this context. Effective communication skills enable employees to understand organizational goals, collaborate effectively with colleagues, and convey ideas. Within the framework of GASM, strong communication skills facilitate the dissemination of sustainability objectives, promote engagement with green initiatives, and foster a culture of environmental stewardship among employees. By enhancing communication channels and promoting transparency, GASM contributes to improved employee morale, productivity, and job satisfaction, ultimately driving better performance outcomes in manufacturing firms. Similarly, time management skills are essential for employees to prioritize tasks, meet deadlines, and optimize productivity. In the context of GASM, efficient time management enables employees to allocate sufficient time and resources toward implementing sustainable practices without compromising on core job responsibilities. By encouraging effective time management practices, GASM ensures that employees can balance their workload effectively, allocate sufficient time for green initiatives, and adapt to changing environmental demands. As a result, employees are better equipped to contribute to organizational sustainability efforts while maintaining high levels of performance and efficiency. We concluded that Green Administrative Skill Management has a significant effect on Employee Performance in manufacturing firms in South Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the observed significant effects of communication skills and time management skills on employee performance within manufacturing firms in South Nigeria, it is imperative to integrate these findings into the implementation of Green Administrative Skill Management (GASM). To maximize the positive impact of GASM on employee performance in this context, the following recommendations are proposed:

- a. Manufacturing firms should prioritize the development of communication skills training programs aimed at enhancing employees' ability to effectively convey and receive information related to environmental sustainability initiatives. These programs should focus on improving verbal and written communication skills, fostering active listening, and promoting interpersonal communication within teams and across departments. By investing in communication skills development, organizations can ensure that employees are better equipped to understand, engage with, and contribute to GASM initiatives, ultimately enhancing their performance and productivity.
- b. Manufacturing firms should offer time management workshops and provide employees with tools and resources to improve their time management skills. These workshops can cover topics such as prioritization, task delegation, and effective scheduling techniques tailored to the demands of GASM implementation. Additionally, the provision of time management software or apps can help employees track their tasks, set deadlines, and allocate time for both core job responsibilities and green initiatives. By empowering employees with effective

time management strategies, organizations can ensure that GASM activities are integrated seamlessly into daily workflows without compromising productivity.

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